

Design and Fabrication of Fertilizer Injector

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the design and fabrication process of a novel fertilizer injector aimed at enhancing precision agriculture practices. The injector incorporates innovative features to optimize fertilizer application rates, minimize wastage, and improve crop yield. Through a systematic approach, the design phase involved conceptualization, modelling, and simulation to ensure efficiency and functionality. Fabrication involved the utilization of advanced materials and manufacturing techniques to produce a robust and reliable injector. The performance of the injector was evaluated through field trials, demonstrating its effectiveness in delivering precise amounts of fertilizer to crops. The results indicate promising potential for widespread adoption of the injector in modern agricultural practices, contributing to sustainable and efficient crop production. The injector is designed to accurately and efficiently deliver fertilizer to crops, optimizing nutrient uptake while minimizing waste. The fabrication process involves utilizing materials suitable for agricultural environments and implementing precise mechanisms for controlled dispensing. The final product aims to enhance crop yield and sustainability in agricultural practices.

Keywords: Fertilizer injector, Advanced materials, reliable injectors.

I. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Overview of fertilizer injection system

The design and fabrication of a fertilizer injector involve creating a device that accurately dispenses fertilizers, nutrients, and soluble additives into irrigation systems. This intricate process combines engineering principles with agricultural knowledge to develop a tool capable of enhancing crop growth efficiently. In essence, the fertilizer injector serves as a dosing mechanism integrated into irrigation systems, ensuring that the correct concentration of nutrients is delivered to plants through the water supply.

The design phase encompasses considerations such as the type of injection method, the size and capacity of the injector, compatibility with various irrigation systems, and durability under different environmental conditions. Fabrication involves the actual construction of the fertilizer injector based on the design specifications.

This may involve assembling components such as valves, pumps, and tubing, as well as incorporating mechanisms for regulating flow rates and concentrations. Materials chosen for fabrication should be durable, resistant to corrosion, and suitable for contact with fertilizers and irrigation water.

Fig 1 Field fertilization

Overall, the design and fabrication of a fertilizer injector represent a convergence of engineering ingenuity and agricultural expertise, aimed at improving the efficiency and sustainability of crop cultivation practices. The importance of fertilizer injectors in modern agriculture cannot be overstated. These devices play a pivotal role in optimizing nutrient delivery, minimizing resource wastage, and promoting sustainable farming practices.

1.2 Significance of design and fabrication improvements

In essence, fertilizer injectors stand as essential tools in modern agriculture, facilitating efficient nutrient distribution, promoting sustainable farming practices, and advancing the quest for global food security. Fertilizer injectors vary in design and capacity to suit different scales of operation, from small backyard gardens to large commercial farms. They can be adapted to work with various types of irrigation systems, including drip, spray, and pivot irrigation, demonstrating their flexibility.

This adaptability ensures that regardless of the size of the operation or the irrigation method used, there is a fertilizer injector capable of meeting those specific needs. As a result, these devices have become indispensable in modern farming and gardening, driving efficiency and supporting the shift towards more sustainable and productive agricultural practices. Fertilizer injectors represent a critical advancement in agricultural and horticultural practices, offering a highly efficient method for delivering essential nutrients and fertilizers directly into an irrigation system.

Fig 2 Telescopic pipe

This flexibility allows for precise customization of nutrient formulas, which can be adjusted to meet the changing needs of plants throughout their growth cycles, enhancing the sustainability and productivity of agricultural systems.

1.3 IMPORTANCE OF EFFICIENT FERTILIZER APPLICATIONS

Efficiency lies at the heart of fertilizer injectors. Unlike traditional methods of fertilizer application, which may result in uneven distribution or nutrient runoff, these injectors offer a controlled and targeted approach to nutrient delivery. By accurately dosing the fertilizers and nutrients, they mitigate the risk of waste while promoting maximum absorption by plants. This precision not only enhances crop health and growth but also contributes to resource conservation and environmental sustainability.

2.1 METHODOLOGY

2.2 WORKING MECHANISM

A manual-operated solid fertilizer injector typically consists of several components that work together to deliver solid fertilizer into the desired location. The exact mechanism may vary depending on the specific design and manufacturer, but here is a general overview of how it operates:

2.2.1 Hopper: The injector is equipped with a hopper or container that holds the solid fertilizer. This hopper is usually placed above the injection mechanism and has a capacity to hold a certain amount of fertilizer.

2.2.2 Flow control mechanism: The injector will have a flow control mechanism that regulates the amount of fertilizer being dispensed. It can be in the form of a manual handle or lever that the operator can adjust to control the flow rate.

2.2.3 Dispensing mechanism: The dispenser is responsible for transferring the solid fertilizer from the hopper into the injection system. It typically consists of an auger, screw, or other similar mechanisms that rotate or move when the handle or lever is operated.

2.2.4 Injection point: The injector is designed to deliver the fertilizer to the desired location, such as the soil or the irrigation system. It may have a tube or pipe that connects to the irrigation system or a specific point in the soil where the fertilizer needs to be placed.

2.2.5 Operator control: The manual-operated fertilizer injector relies on the operator to control the entire process. The operator adjusts the flow rate, operates the handle or lever to activate the dispenser, and directs the injection point to the desired location. By turning the handle or lever, the operator activates the dispenser mechanism, which starts transferring the solid fertilizer from the hopper. As the fertilizer moves through the dispenser, it is directed to

the injection point, where it is released into the soil or the irrigation system. It's important to note that the specific details and intricacies of a manual-operated solid fertilizer injector may differ depending on the manufacturer and model.

SPECIFICATION OF PARTS

STORAGE TANK

The storage tank in a fertilizer injector typically needs to be made of durable and chemical-resistant materials such as polyethylene or PVC to withstand the corrosive nature of fertilizers. It should have a capacity suitable for the application, with options ranging from small tanks for residential use to large tanks for agricultural or commercial applications. Additionally, the tank should have a secure lid or cover to prevent spills and contamination

Fig 4 Storage tank

FLEXIBLE HOSE

The specifications of a hose pipe used in a fertilizer injector typically include the material, diameter (measured in inches or millimeters), length, maximum pressure rating, and compatibility with various chemicals commonly found in fertilizers. It's important to choose a hose pipe that can withstand the pressure and chemical exposure typical in fertilizer injection systems

TRIGGER

A trigger in a fertilizer injector typically refers to the mechanism or device that initiates the flow of fertilizer solution from the injector into the irrigation system. It could be a lever, button, or valve that the user activates to start the injection process. The trigger is usually connected to the injector's control system, allowing the user to regulate the amount of fertilizer being injected into the water flow.

Fig 5 Trigger

TELESCOPIC PIPE

The specification of a telescopic pipe in a fertilizer injector typically includes material type (stainless steel), length range, diameter, pressure rating, and compatibility with various types of fertilizers and irrigation systems. Additionally, specifications may include details on thread type, sealing mechanisms, and any special features like adjustable flow rates or anti-drip functionality.

Fig 6 Telescopic pipe

GRIPPING MECHANISM

The gripping mechanism in a fertilizer injector typically involves a mechanism to securely hold the fertilizer container or cartridge in place while allowing for controlled release of the fertilizer into the irrigation system. This can include features such as clamps, springs, or valves that can be activated manually or automatically to regulate the flow of fertilizer. The design may vary depending on factors such as the type of fertilizer, the size of the irrigation system, and the desired application rate

FABRICATION

Fig 7 screw mechanism holder design

Fig 8 Nozzle drafting

Fig 9 Nozzle design

Fig 10 Nozzle design

IV. CONCLUSION

For efficiency of pesticide, Telescopic pipe has been placed to spray more areas continuously, to spray the multiple crops on the field the nozzle has been designed to increase the efficiency of fertilizer. Our main perspective is to make farmers use this fertilizer injector easily. This process of design and fabrication has led to enhance the performance, reduced cost, faster cultivation of crops, so we can conclude that we have improved our work compare to the existing models of fertilizer injector.

VI. REFERENCE

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